

ETHNOBOTANICAL STUDY OF MEDICINAL PLANTS WITH GASTROPROTECTIVE EFFECTS IN THE WANAYASA REGION, PURWAKARTA, WEST JAVA, INDONESIA

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ABSTRACT

Peptic ulcers result from an imbalance between protective factors (e.g., prostaglandins, nitric oxide, and sulfhydryl groups) and aggressive risk factors (e.g., consumption of non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs, alcohol, or tobacco) regarding the gastric mucosa. While various existing treatments aim to relieve pain, repair the ulcer, and prevent its recurrence, they often produce undesirable side effects. This research aims to document and preserve the use of ethnomedicine to gastroprotective by people in the Wanayasa Region, Purwakarta, West Java, Indonesia. Fieldwork was carried out from November to December 2025 using direct interviews, questionnaires, and discussions. Plant species are identified based on standard taxonomic methods, flower morphological characteristics, and where possible, using samples for comparison, as well as consultation with experts and the literature. The plant types obtained were grouped into families according to the Cronquist classification system. Plant names were checked against the Plant List (www.plantlist.org) and the International Plant Name Index (www.ipni.org). This research reports that 30 plant species are commonly used by people in the Wanayasa Region to gastroprotective. Among the various plant parts used, leaves (63.3%) are most frequently used in making medicines, followed by rhizomes (13.3%), fruit (6.7%), flowers (6.7%), stem, rind, and seed (respectively 3.3%). Meanwhile, the most frequently used preparation methods were decoction (76.7%) and infusion (23.3%). The results of this research confirm that people in the Wanayasa Region still rely heavily on medicinal plants for their health care system, especially for the gastroprotective with the most frequently used parts of the leaves and their use in decoctions and infusions.

KEYWORDS: Traditional medicine, Ethnomedicinal plants, Wanayasa Region, Gastroprotective.

INTRODUCTION

The gastrointestinal mucosa is a thick layer of mucus that acts a barrier against invading pathogens, and also protects the underlying tissues from the digestive juices. When various factors and components of mucosal defense are insufficient to limit injury to the mucosa, an ulcer forms.^[1] Peptic ulcers are lesions that form when the digestive juices containing hydrochloric acid (HCl) corrode the gastric mucosal lining, which can lead to gastrointestinal bleeding, gastric perforation, and even gastric cancer.^[2] Gastric damage and ulcers can be

induced by drinking, smoking, stress, poor diet and pathogenic infections. High concentrations of ethanol directly corrode the gastric mucosal tissue, causing inflammation, mucosal congestion, edema, bleeding, mucosal erosion and ulcers.^[3] Although the exact pathological basis of gastric ulcer is unknown, oxidative stress and inflammation have been implicated as the main driving factors.^[4] Oxidative damage to the gastric epithelial and the ensuing apoptosis also play an important role in the progression of gastric diseases.^[5] The repairment of gastric ulcers is a highly regulated and

complicated process involving inhibition of inflammation and promotion of cell proliferation, formation of granulation tissue and angiogenesis.^[1] Currently, peptic ulcers are treated with H₂-receptor blockers (ranitidine), proton pump inhibitors (omeprazole) and cytoprotectants (carbenoxolone, sucralfate, misoprostol, bismuth chelate), which reduce the morbidity rates but are also associated with side effects.^[6]

Research to obtain new drugs to gastroprotective originating from natural ingredients continues to be carried out, one of which is through exploring active compounds from natural ingredients, especially medicinal plants which have traditionally been used by people to gastroprotective in various countries, especially Indonesia.^[7,8] One of the Region in Indonesia that still uses herbal plants as an alternative treatment, especially for gastroprotective, is Wanayasa Region. This research aims to obtain detailed information about the use of herbal plants for alternative therapy for gastroprotective in Wanayasa Region, Purwakarta, West Java, Indonesia using a field survey method.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Area

Wanayasa is located in Purwakarta Regency, West Java, Indonesia, with an area of 24.83 km². This area has an altitude of 736 meters above sea level with an average maximum air temperature of 27°C and a minimum of 17°C. Moreover, it is located between 06°40' 56" South Latitude and 107°33' 30" East Longitude. This area is a tropical climate area that is mostly inhabited by Sundanese tribes (98%) and other tribes (2%). Vegetation in the study area is in humid conditions with an average rainfall of 3,093 mm/year.

Data Collection

An extensive field survey was carried out to obtain information about medicinal plants from the Sundanese tribe in the study area. To document existing information about medicinal plants from tribal practitioners, several field visits were conducted from November to December 2025 in the Wanayasa Region, Purwakarta, West Java,

Indonesia. During the research, ethnomedicinal information was collected from middle-aged and older tribal practitioners in their local language (Sundanese), through direct interviews, questionnaires, and discussions. Information on local names of plants, plant parts used, preparation methods and administration routes (e.g., infusion, paste, juice and decoction) of all ethnomedicinal plants collected were recorded during the survey period.

Botanical Identification

Plant species are identified based on standard taxonomic methods, flower morphological characteristics, and where possible, using samples for comparison, as well as consultation with experts and the literature.^[9] The plant types obtained were grouped into families according to the Cronquist classification system, except for Pteridophyta and Gymnospermae.^[10] Plant names were checked against the Plant List (www.plantlist.org) and the International Plant Name Index (www.ipni.org).

Ethics Statement

All participants provided verbal consent before the interview and gave consent to publish the information they provided.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This research revealed that 30 plant species are commonly used by local people to gastroprotective (Table 1). This shows that the study location is affordable in terms of biodiversity. Among the various plant parts used, leaves (63.3%) are most frequently used in making medicines, followed by rhizomes (13.3%), fruit (6.7%), flowers (6.7%), stem, rind, and seed (respectively 3.3%). The use of leaves is reported to be easier to prepare and easier to extract active substances from them for treatment. At the same time, leaves have less effect on the mother plant.^[11] Meanwhile, the most frequently used preparation methods were decoction (76.7%) and infusion (23.3%). These results are in line with previous research which reported that the forms of traditional medicine most widely used by the community were decoctions and infusions.^[9]

Table 1: Ethnomedicinal plants, local name, part used, mode of administration, and dosage uses in Wanayasa, Purwakarta, West Java, Indonesia.

No	Species	Family	Local name	Parts used	Mode of administration	Dosage of use
1	<i>Abrus precatorius</i> L.	Fabaceae	Saga	Leaf	Decoction	50 grams once a day
2	<i>Allium cepa</i> L.	Amaryllidaceae	Bawang Bombai	Rhizome	Decoction	80 grams once a day
3	<i>Allium sativum</i> L.	Alliaceae	Bawang Putih	Rhizome	Infusion	50 grams once a day
4	<i>Aloe vera</i> Burm.f.	Asphodelaceae	Lidah Buaya	Stem	Decoction	100 grams once a day
5	<i>Alpinia galanga</i> L.	Zingiberaceae	Lengkuas	Rhizome	Decoction	10 grams once a day
6	<i>Andrographis paniculata</i> Nees	Acanthaceae	Sambiloto	Leaf	Decoction	50 grams once a day
7	<i>Annona muricata</i> L.	Annonaceae	Sirsak	Leaf	Infusion	100 grams once a day
8	<i>Carica papaya</i> L.	Caricaceae	Pepaya	Leaf	Decoction	100 grams once a day
9	<i>Ceiba pentandra</i> (L.) Gaertn.	Malvaceae	Kapuk	Leaf	Decoction	10 grams once a day

10	<i>Cinnamomum verum</i> J. Presl.	Lauraceae	Kayu Manis	Stem	Decoction	50 grams once a day
11	<i>Cordia dikotoma</i> G. Forst.	Boraginaceae	Kendal	Stem	Decoction	10 grams once a day
12	<i>Curcuma longa</i> L.	Zingiberaceae	Kunyit	Rhizome	Infusion	100 grams once a day
13	<i>Curcuma xanthorrhiza</i> Roxb	Zingiberaceae	Temulawak	Rhizome	Decoction	50 grams once a day
14	<i>Garcinia mangostana</i> L.	Clusiaceae	Manggis	Rind	Infusion	100 grams once a day
15	<i>Jatropha gossypifolia</i> L.	Euphorbiaceae	Jarak	Leaf	Decoction	100 grams once a day
16	<i>Kaempferia galanga</i> L.	Zingiberaceae	Kencur	Rhizome	Infusion	250 grams once a day
17	<i>Manilkara zapota</i> (L.) P. Royen	Sapotaceae	Sawo	Leaf	Decoction	50 grams once a day
18	<i>Momordica charantia</i> L.	Cucurbitaceae	Pare	Leaf	Decoction	10 grams once a day
19	<i>Morinda citrifolia</i> L.	Rubiaceae	Mengkudu	Fruit	Infusion	50 grams once a day
20	<i>Moringa oleifera</i> Lamk.	Moringaceae	Kelor	Leaf	Decoction	50 grams once a day
21	<i>Myristica fragrans</i> Houtt.	Myristicaceae	Pala	Seed	Decoction	50 grams once a day
22	<i>Nigella sativa</i> L.	Ranunculaceae	Jinten Hitam	Seed	Decoction	10 grams once a day
23	<i>Paederia foetida</i> L.	Rubiaceae	Daun Kentut	Leaf	Decoction	50 grams once a day
24	<i>Pandanus amaryllifolius</i> Roxb.	Pandanaceae	Pandan	Leaf	Infusion	50 grams once a day
25	<i>Persea americana</i> Mill.	Lauraceae	Alpukat	Leaf	Decoction	10 grams once a day
26	<i>Piper betle</i> L.	Piperaceae	Sirih	Leaf	Decoction	100 grams once a day
27	<i>Sauropus androgynus</i> Merr.	Phyllanthaceae	Katuk	Leaf	Decoction	100 grams once a day
28	<i>Tinospora crispa</i> L.	Menispermaceae	Baratawali	Leaf	Decoction	10 grams once a day
29	<i>Ziziphus mauritiana</i> Lam.	Rhamnaceae	Bidara	Leaf	Decoction	20 grams once a day
30	<i>Zingiber officinale</i> Rosc.	Zingiberaceae	Jahe	Rhizome	Decoction	50 grams once a day

CONCLUSIONS

The results of this research confirm that people in the Wanayasa Region still rely heavily on medicinal plants for their health care system, especially for the gastroprotective with the most frequently used parts of the leaves and their use in decoctions and infusions.

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